

Sustainability Determinants of NGO Projects in Lebanon

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Abstract

The dynamic and changing environment and the critical crisis in Lebanon make it hard for NGOs to survive and thrive. This means that the NGOs should make the right decisions and implement strategies to cope with any environmental change.

This research paper aims to find the following factors: Staff competency, Institutional democracy, project manager leadership style, stakeholder involvement, financing impact, environmental impact, and governmental policies that might influence sustainability. This research paper aims to test the relationship between those factors and sustainability.

The quantitative method was used to determine this relationship. A questionnaire was designed and created to test the hypothesis and achieve the research objectives.

The results of this study showed that there is a positive relationship between the factors and sustainability itself. The financial aspect then stakeholder's involvement are the most significant factors that influence sustainability in NGOs in Lebanon. This is followed by staff competence and environmental impact. However, leadership, institutional democracy, and governmental policies have little impact on sustainability. This shows the importance of finance and stakeholders' involvement when it comes to the growth and sustainability of NGOs. International NGOs in Lebanon must receive and maintain funding to sustain in this changing situation, in addition, stakeholders should be kept involved in project implementation of activities and plans. International NGOs must create and implement the right strategies to sustain and continue in these tough times in Lebanon.

Keywords: Sustainability, NGO Projects, Staff Competence, Leadership Style, Institutional Democracy, Stakeholders Involvement, Finance, Environmental Impact, Governmental Policies.

Introduction

Sustainability has gained familiarity in research, business development, and the social sector over the last decades. With the demand for more services, a dynamic environment, and rare resources, an organization must face the challenges, and formulate and create any resources to face any challenges. The success of the NGO will be determined by how the strategies fit with such factors as the environment, competencies and resources, and the aspirations of the managers and stakeholders. This research paper aims to investigate the factors that influence the sustainability of NGOs. It aims to determine the impact of those factors on the sustainability of NGOs in Lebanon.

The impact and influence of those factors are being tested and analyzed using quantitative methods of research. Quantitative research is the path towards getting valuable insights and understanding how those factors might have an impact on the sustainability of the NGO. A survey was created and distributed to international NGOs in Lebanon to reach the results needed to conclude. Recently, Lebanon has been experiencing increased levels of poverty, conflict, and refugee crisis. This has led to increased NGO activities in that region, mostly focused on providing humanitarian support and long-term projects that require sustainability. This would help project managers and NGO leaders in managing and executing their NGO projects more effectively and with a wider, long-term impact. Therefore, this study is needed for two main reasons: first, as a result of the crisis that has impacted Lebanon since 2019, and which had economic, social,

and health consequences on the population, especially in the crisis Lebanon is facing. according to studies from 2021 (UNDP, List of NGOs by Affiliation Type, 2021), the number of NGOs increased in 2021 to more than 400. The second reason is that, lately donors are requesting sustainability of projects in their reports, and therefore it becomes important to explore what are the determinants of sustainability in such projects.

The core problem that many NGOs face in their projects is the lack of project sustainability characterized by projects that are limited in their duration and resources and, therefore in their impact as well. This prevents NGOs from attracting the necessary funding for future projects and creating the lasting impact that they wish to have. Additionally, recently donors have asked for the sustainability requirement description in the proposals submitted for the project. Accordingly, this makes it important for them to follow best practices in ensuring the sustainability of their projects and consequently the sustainability of their impact and the opportunities, which sustainable projects provide to NGOs and their respective communities.

Research Questions

The main questions which this research aims to answer are:

1. What are the main determinants for the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
2. How does staff competence affect the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
3. How does the project manager's leadership style influence the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
4. How does institutional democracy within the NGO affect the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
5. How does stakeholder involvement affect the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
6. How does financing impact the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
7. How does the project's environment impact the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?
8. How do government policies influence the sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon?

Literature Review

NGO projects are not permanent interventions; they have specified end dates. Consequently, donors aim to gradually reduce support at the project level for various aspects when providing funding. This is primarily done to ensure the long-term sustainability of their projects or programs. Additionally, a comprehensive evaluation of exit strategies in aid programs by multiple donors revealed that planning for a proper exit and sustainability is more of an exception than a rule (Heldgaar, 2008). According to the European Environment Agency (2004), sustainability is defined as the continuous flow of benefits generated from a project even after external support has ceased. Project sustainability involves development efforts that meet current needs without jeopardizing the ability to meet future requirements (World Bank, 2019).

Main Determinants for Sustainable NGO Projects

Sustainable NGO projects are crucial for addressing various social, economic, and environmental challenges. Identifying and understanding the main determinants for sustainable NGO projects involves considering a range of factors. The following outlines and explains some key determinants for sustainable NGO projects:

Staff Competence

The competence of NGO staff is crucial for project success. A study by Masoud and Basahal (2023) emphasized that staff with diverse skills and expertise contribute to effective project implementation, ensuring adaptability to various challenges. An essential element in staff qualifications and competencies, which in turn helps in ensuring the project's sustainability and continuation in the NGO, relates to the quality of the guidance of the project manager and his ability to positively influence, develop, and motivate his team (Rachin, 2001).

According to Nongo (2009), it prevents the organizational problem of ineffective management styles which can negatively affect the performance of non-governmental organizations in the long run, and so, the sustainability of their projects. This is especially the case during times of crisis when the need for change and transformation becomes imminent, yet there are no proper and effective management styles, calibers, and attitudes that can help assist the organization in adapting to the changes and sustaining itself throughout the project management process (Nongo, 2009). Organizations are composed of people who continuously execute their roles with reservations to complete their objectives as required (Adebakin & Gbadamosi, 1996). The various elements within an organization need to interrelate to ensure the realization of the objectives and goals. As such, the important elements within an organization are time, people, and activities that require redress through supervision. Here, management provides an important aspect in the continuous provision of approaches that will influence organizational people to achieve their corporate goals. Specifically, Managers influence people through the proper administration of money and material resources within the organization. Management research offers an ideal approach to providing policies, regulations, and procedures that govern the conduct of relationships within an organization. Consequently, proper management of an organization results

in increasing the effectiveness of responsibilities and achieving corporate goals. In an organizational environment, it is possible to have two or more people interacting and the presence of a common objective will be the basis of the organization to persist for a longer period.

Stakeholder Involvement

Active involvement of stakeholders is vital for project sustainability. As indicated by Pretty et al. (1995), projects that incorporate the perspectives and engagement of local communities and beneficiaries are more likely to be sustainable and aligned with the actual needs of the target population. According to findings from the literature, stakeholder involvement is in two areas: For Amico (2014) first, in the community where the NGO is executing the project. Second, within the NGO itself. The stakeholders in the community should be involved in the project especially when it targets it. Otherwise, the community would feel sidelined and would not support the project (Amico, 2014). The bottom line here is to ensure a continuous flow of net benefits to all stakeholders: the community, the project team, and the sponsors.

According to the article ‘Towards “Shareholder Spring” in the Middle East?’ (2014), “The events witnessed in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region over the past 3 years have resulted in a profound questioning of the economic and social pact in some countries of the region. And yet, the role of corporations as main actors of wealth generation and distribution has not been subject to much debate” (Amico, 2014, p.1). This highlights the key role of stakeholder activism within the context of corporate governance. Together, these concepts can help in improving the country’s economic integrity and productivity, because stakeholder activism that leads to good corporate governance can help in solving long-term and immediate challenges in Lebanon.

To improve the role of stakeholders and ensure they help in building more profitable, sustainable competitive, corruption-free NGO projects, the research importantly shows that for corporate governments to serve the interest of societies and NGOs, it can’t be imposed through regulatory requirements as is the case in most MENA region markets: the shareholders, especially those that are major institutional actors, should be part of the process on how NGOs can take a more proactive and profitable role in the region’s future. In this regard, an important emphasis should be given to the concept of stakeholder theory. According to the research, the stakeholder theory gives priority to the shareholder or the owners’ view in an NGO (Solomon, 2007). The NGO and its officials have a binding duty to increase the value for the shareholders by prioritizing their needs first (Solomon, 2007). According to that theory, there are other parties involved, including suppliers, employees, financiers, customers, governmental bodies, trade associations, political groups, trade unions, and other communities who are considered stakeholders.

Financial Aspects

Financial considerations are fundamental to sustaining NGO projects. According to Yaziji and Doh (2009), securing adequate and diversified funding sources enhances financial resilience, mitigating the risk of project failure due to budget constraints. Many economists in the world have seen that financing the development of small NGO projects and the encouragement of their establishment, is one of the most important tributaries of the process of economic and social development in countries in general, and developing countries in the third world in particular (Smillie, Helmich, Randel and German, 2013). It supports project sustainability because it is a basic starting point for increasing community capacity on the one hand and contributing to addressing the problems of poverty and unemployment. Therefore, many countries have given these projects increasing attention and provided them with assistance and assistance in various ways and according to the available possibilities for financing through several financing sectors (Smillie, Helmich, Randel, and German, 2013).

Moreover, an important element in project financing is the equitable sharing and distribution of project benefits, which would help sustain the project further. According to the World Bank (2019) if the project’s benefits are not shared equally and equitably, it would not last long since it would lose support and fall apart. For an equitable sharing of project benefits, this requires transparency and good governance throughout the project’s value chain. The absence of this transparency can negatively impact not only the project but also the organization or companies (World Bank, 2019).

On the general level, one report from the World Bank discussed the lack of transparency and equitable sharing and distribution of project benefits in the Middle East region. The report asserts that much of the slowdown in growth in the Middle East and North Africa is due to a lack of transparency. “The decline in transparency in the Middle East and North Africa between 2005 and 2018 correlates with the projected loss of per capita income in the region, which ranges between 7% and 14%,” said Daniel Lederman, Vice President Economist at the World Bank and lead author of the report (World Bank, 2019, p.1). It is the only region where data capabilities and transparency have decreased since 2005, as a result of the collective inequitable sharing and distribution of benefits among projects.

On the community level, Ball (2009) mentions that equitable sharing of project benefits would help in sustaining it because it would maintain the interest and the trust of the community members: they would feel that the project supports

them all fairly, and would not feel alienated, neglected or unfairly left out by the project and its team. This would encourage the community members to support the NGO's projects again.

Leadership Skills

Effective leadership is a key determinant. In his work, Yukl (2013) argued that leadership skills, including vision setting, motivation, and decision-making, significantly impact project success and organizational sustainability. Leadership as a phenomenon is a systematic process of influencing people within an organization to move in a particular direction. The degree to which individuals demonstrate their leadership capabilities is greatly influenced by their traits, abilities, and personality (Messick & Krammer, 2004). However, the characteristics in the external environment play a pivotal role in influencing the success of leadership in an organization. Ordinarily, people within an organization will support their leadership where personal objectives and aims are properly addressed. Consequently, leadership is exhibited where a single person in a group is capable of modifying and influencing others by motivation. According to Nongo (2009), leadership is demonstrated in an instance where there is an unequal distribution of power within an organization. However, leadership is important in an organization because it is linked to the practice that followers are dedicated to achieving (Rachin, 2001).

In an organization, a leader has the responsibility of developing and managing corporate change. Here, leadership focuses on the establishment of a suitable workplace environment that will be ready to adopt a necessary change. For example, through organizational culture, changes can be implemented by a leader through the development of novel strategies in the process of change management. Leadership provides a basis for interconnecting organizational people alongside the processes (Appelbaum, 1998). In the modern business environment, the evolution and use of technologies in promoting success have become a crucial part of organizations. Leadership plays a pivotal role in the context because it is the basis of managing new technologies. For instance, transactional and transformational are two theories of leadership that serve to properly manage technologies within an organization. In particular, a transactional leader will focus on implementing technological changes to acquire technical skills. However, its limitation is that it does not focus much on people and approaches to problem-solving. Therefore, leadership plays a vital role in an organization especially based on management, performance, and implementing organizational change processes (Weick and Quinn, 1999). Managing an organization is a process that is influenced by both internal and external factors that have an impact on different situations and scenarios. For example, organizational culture is crucial in influencing the change processes. As such, leadership is critical in developing a culture that will support change, motivate employees, and provide a vision for the organization (Weick and Quinn, 1999). In the end, effective leadership within an organization has a positive impact on organizational performance, management of change processes, innovations, and achievement of corporate objectives.

Environmental Impact

Considering the environmental impact of projects is essential for long-term sustainability. The Brundtland Report (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987) highlighted the importance of environmentally conscious practices for sustainable development. Onkoba (2016) indicates the significance of participatory resource mobilization in realizing effective project performance and reducing the possibility of project failure. Another significant factor is the project design in which the project is developed based on the local demand and the commitment of the local institutions and community members in improving the effectiveness of such a project. Local community members can highlight the significance of the project donors in focusing on environmental conservation while providing sustainable measures to improve the success of the project. Environmental awareness should be prioritized with the community made aware of the sustainability issues towards realizing mutually acceptable projects.

Project sustainability in NGOs can also be maintained by ensuring that the project does not reduce the capacity of the environment to provide for future generations, while at the same time meeting the demands of its surrounding environment. According to Bansal and Roth (2000), several motivators drive NGOs to go green beyond ecological responsiveness; and these motivators include market competitiveness and the legitimacy of their operations and waste emissions. Many managers consider the green approach as costly because improvements must be applied to the utilities, maintenance techniques, and building design of the business that decides to go green (Nalewaik & Venters, 2009). For example, Within the Lebanese context, and as part of the UNDP-CEDRO project (which is an NGO project), the implementation of Solar Hot Water (SWH) systems, Photovoltaic systems (PV), and Ground-source heat pumps (GSHP) at more than 10 Lebanese hospitals and schools, were supported (Harajli, 2012). These improvements, for which a budget of 9.73 million USD was allocated, were intended to reduce energy costs with the support of sustainable energy utilities. The fact that adopting such technologies by businesses could be costly is undeniable; however, the sustainable outcome of such practices is directly translated into cost efficiency and sustainable cost reduction in the long run.

Many activists in the environmental field expressed an interest in providing support and a sense of direction to businesses interested in adopting eco-friendly practices, and several non-profit organizations were founded for this purpose, with their main concern being to introduce legislation tackling this type of NGO activity. Until this date, the implementation

of "green" approaches in NGO projects is a matter of choice. In other words, NGOs might choose to operate while controlling the environmental damage caused by their projects or by their day-to-day operations. Thus, by operating in an eco-friendly manner, the NGO is fulfilling its civic duties towards the community (Logsdon, 2004). This is also known as Corporate Environmental Responsibility, which, according to Cretney (2005) involves "a comprehensive view of the environmental community's expectations of NGOs that claim to be environmentally responsible". On the other hand, contemporary studies have shown that "green" NGO projects enjoy several advantages beyond their environmental benefit, and this includes sustainability. One important benefit that is yielded from going green in NGO project management would be improving the NGO's image in the eyes of the community.

Government Policy

The regulatory environment and government policies play a crucial role. According to Ingram and Schneider (1990), alignment with government policies and regulations enhances the legitimacy of NGO projects, contributing to their sustainability. Moreover, the sustainability of NGO projects requires the support and policies of governments to ensure these projects can fulfill their objectives and prolong themselves. Mainly, the government support would be in the form of infrastructure, security, and legislation that facilitate the application of the project (Chan and Li, 2016).

Governmental institutions, experts, policymakers, and officials should also assist NGOs in developing internal governance systems. In this context, Logsdon (2004) explains the leader in the organization can take part in establishing the democratic structure of NGOs by exerting efforts in the following axes as explained by multiple authors:

1. Setting the general objective and soundly phrasing the mission of the association:
The leader should help emphasize the importance of the role that the mission statement plays in ensuring its continuity and creating a spirit of belonging to the association (Nikkhah and Redzuan, 2010).
2. Motivating actual participation in institutional volunteer work:
Internal democratic governance achieves the maximum possible degree of participation of the members of the association and its main audience in the decision-making processes and policy-making for work (Logsdon, 2004). Establish mechanisms to achieve institutional transparency:
3. Internal governance is a system that achieves a greater area of transparency in dealing, so the leader should design systems and organizational means that help the association provide means of knowledge and ensure the flow of information about the organization to all members and stakeholders (Klugman, 2000).
4. Ensuring full accountability for members and officials:
Internal democratic governance is built based on a full sense of the ability to bear responsibility and the consequences related to work, and therefore the center works to ensure accountability of members of boards of directors (Klugman, 2000).
5. Diversity of ideas within a single association:
To encourage the organization to adopt systems that provide the opportunity within the association for freedom of opinion and the formation of different points of view and considers that the difference of visions is a healthy phenomenon that works to develop work and strengthen feelings of belonging to the association (Mercer, 2002).
6. Establishing accurate systems for fair elections to make democratic decisions in the assembly:
The organization leaders should make sure that internal democratic governance is always divided into democratically elected councils and committees on sound grounds (Mercer, 2002). This allows the largest number of individuals to participate and rotate responsibility in the various government agencies.
7. Encouraging leadership rotation and power rotation in the association:
According to Mercer (2002), the leader should work on developing new leaders and emphasizing the exchange of leadership within the same association, and to achieve a practical reality of power exchange within the internal governance bodies.

Institutional Democracy

Democracy means "the opportunity that society provides for its members to participate freely in making decisions in different aspects of life (Dahl, Shapiro, and Hacker-Cordon, 1999). This concept of democracy includes a variety of standards, and these standards, in turn, translate into behaviors, beliefs, and values, which should be maintained by the leader in a non-governmental organization to ensure a democratic organizational culture. The authors contend that Democracy involves:

1. Appreciation of the process of participating in decision-making.
2. Ensuring and protecting the expression of opinion, acceptance of the other opinion recognition of its existence, and respect for opponents' opinion.
3. The full responsibility of every individual for his actions and actions.
4. Faith and concern for human rights, and the rejection of all forms of exploitation or subjugation of others.
5. Achieving justice and equality among members of society, regardless of the differences between them, whether based on sex, gender, affiliation, or any other form of discrimination.

6. Provide the opportunity for every citizen to meet with other citizens, to take effective initiatives in a conscious and positive development.

Institutional democracy fosters inclusivity and participatory decision-making. Gupta and Vegelin (2016) noted that NGOs with democratic governance structures are more likely to generate community trust and support, essential for sustained project impact.

In conclusion, a comprehensive understanding and integration of these determinants can significantly contribute to the sustainability of NGO projects. However, it is important to note that the success of each project may depend on its unique context, and a nuanced approach considering these factors in tandem is often necessary. Thus, this research will adopt the above seven variables in studying their influence on project sustainability.

Methodology

Research Approach

Based on the goal of this research, the deductive approach will be followed. This approach starts from the general (theory) to the specific (particular evidence and numerical data) (Liu, 2016). Accordingly, the hypothesis (theory) and research question will mark the beginning of this research after which data collection will test its validity. At the end of the research, the findings from the gathered data would either accept or reject the hypothesis.

The justification for choosing the deductive approach is that there is limited information available on the subject under study (sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon), and as such it moves from exploring the available information from secondary and primary sources before finally reaching a specific conclusion.

Research Purpose

This research uses a quantitative methodology through the use of a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire had 33 questions that measured the different variables being tested, targeting a sample of international NGO workers active in the project management and implementation field. From a total of 43 targeted respondents as per UNDP research (UNDP, List of NGOs by Affiliation Type, 2021) 23 sent back their answers, which makes the response rate around 58%.

Data Analysis and Findings

The data collected was examined using means, variances, and computations displayed using tables for quantitative data. Quantitative data was examined using SPSS, to get the statistical mean to describe the general tendency of the data set, the standard deviation to measure the spread of data around the mean, and multiple linear regression as inferential statistics. Multiple linear regression was applied to calculate the relationship between dependent and independent variables using coefficients as correlation and coefficient of determination and significance level.

Descriptive Statistics

When asked whether staff competence influences the sustainability of NGO projects in their country, the vast majority (84%) agreed. Also, 48% agreed that staff knowledge of the most important issues for stakeholders is essential for the success of the project.

Moreover, 36% said that staff specialization and technical competence are key to the project's sustainability, and 16% said that a project can succeed or fail in sustainability because of a lack of staff competence skills.

When it came to leadership skills, the vast majority of the respondents 72% said that the project manager's leadership skills determine the project's sustainability. This finding appears to be consistent with another finding where 28% of the respondents said that a project result can be a success or failure because of leadership skills.

Moreover, speaking of institutional democracy, 56% of the respondents said that institutional democracy within the NGO influences the sustainability of the project. Another finding 24% of the respondents said that a project result can be a success or failure because of Institutional democracy, however, 20% stated that there is no effect on sustainability.

In addition, 52% said that financing and the availability of funds influence the sustainability of NGO projects, and 44% said that stakeholder involvement has an impact on the NGO project's sustainability in the country, besides the fact that the involvement of these stakeholders determines the effectiveness of the project (44%). The same applies to financial management, where 56% said that it is a key factor that influences the success of the project implementation.

The environment was also a factor that played a critical role in the sustainability of the project, according to 44% of the respondents, in addition to forecasting the financial effects and risks of the project. (36% gave it the importance of 4/5). In addition, when asked about the impact of government policies, 36% agreed that they have a heavy impact on project sustainability, giving them a 5/5 rating, while the majority of 32% gave a 4/5 importance level for the impact of the coordination with government bodies on the success of project implementation.

Also, a majority of 44% said that they believe NGO projects are sustainable while only 20% said that they do not think they are sustainable, and 16% claimed that it is neither (in between)

Factor	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly agree
Staff Competence	0%	0%	16%	48%	36%
Leadership style	0%	0%	28%	36%	36%
Institutional democracy	8%	12%	24%	28%	28%
Stakeholder's Involvement	0%	0%	8%	48%	44%
Finance	0%	0%	4%	44%	52%
Environmental impact	0%	8%	12%	44%	36%
Government policies	0%	12%	20%	32%	36%
Sustainability	4%	16%	20%	40%	20%

Table 2. Statistical percentages answers of the survey

Mean and standard deviation of the variables

The sustainability variable has an average of 3.75 and a standard deviation of 0.91235. This shows the sustainability variable is centered around 3.75 and there is a good variation among the answers. The Staff Competence average is around 3.4 and the standard deviation is 1.118. This shows that the average answers of the respondents are around 3.5 and there is a high variation in the answers of the respondents. The Leadership variable has an average of 3.29 and a standard deviation of 1.09. This shows that the leadership variable answers are centered around 3.3 and it has good variation. The institute Democracy has a variable of 2.9584 and the standard is 0.9. This indicates that this variable has an average of 3 and the variable has a good variation in its answers. The stakeholder involvement variable has an average of 3.8 and the standard is 1.16 which means good variation in answers. The average answers in the Finance section are around 4.14 and the standard is around 0.9 indicating good variation. The environmental variable has a variation of 2.966 and a standard of 1.24. The governmental variable has a mean of 2.5964 and a standard deviation of 1.17. This shows high levels of variables.

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Sustainability	3.7500	0.91235	25
Staff Competence	3.4652	1.11819	25
Leadership Style	3.2959	1.09688	25
Institutional Democracy	2.9584	0.97836	25
Stakeholder Involvement	3.8391	1.16191	25
Finance	4.1472	0.91929	25
Environmental Impact	2.9666	1.24140	25
Governmental Policy	2.5964	1.17622	25

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation of the determinants of sustainability

Inferential Statistical and Hypothesis Testing using Linear Regression

Linear regression was performed to measure and determine the impact of the factors of sustainability on the sustainability itself. Linear regression can help to prove the hypothesis and answer the research questions stated in this research paper. The results of the linear regression in Table 4, showed that the R squared of this model is 0.999 which is considered high. The R squared indicates that all the variables stated of sustainability represent and 90% of the variability observed in the target variable is explained by the regression model. It also shows that 99% of the variation in the Sustainability variable is explained by the factors. The adjusted R square is a corrected goodness of fit for the linear regression model. It

decreased a little bit indicating that fewer variables will create better results and that if more variables were added, the R squared would be 0.997.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.999 ^a	0.997	0.996	0.05606	0.997	905.76	7	17	0

Table 4. R squared - Predictors: (Constant), Governmental, Finance, Leadership, Institution Democracy, Staff Competence, Environmental, stakeholder's involvement

Coefficients:

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.224	0.058		3.88	0.001
Staff Competence	0.147	0.022	0.18	6.575	0
Leadership Style	0.072	0.017	0.087	4.161	0.001
Institutional Democracy	0.019	0.019	0.02	0.967	0.347
Stakeholder Involvement	0.255	0.033	0.324	7.78	0
Finance	0.313	0.036	0.315	8.74	0
Environmental Impact	0.12	0.023	0.164	5.302	0
Governmental Policy	0.035	0.022	0.045	1.557	0

Table 5. Linear regression: Dependent Variable: Sustainability

The results in Table 5 showed that there is a positive relationship between all the independent variables and sustainability.

$$Y = 0.022 + 0.147X_1 + 0.072 X_2 + 0.019 X_3 + 0.255 X_4 + 0.0313 X_5 + 0.12 X_6 + 0.035 X_7$$

The Results showed that if all the variables are held constant or at zero, the value of sustainability of the project would be 0.022.

There is a positive relationship between staff competency and the sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more competent the staff is, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.147). This shows that a unit increase in staff competency can lead to a 0.147 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between the leadership and sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more competent and efficient leaders there are, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.072). One unit increase in leadership will lead to a 0.072 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between the institution's democracy and the sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that if the institution has democracy, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.019). This shows that a unit increase in interstitial democracy will lead to a 0.019 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between stakeholder involvement and the sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more the stakeholders are involved, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.225). One unit increase in stakeholder involvement will lead to a 0.225 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between the finance and sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more there are funds, the more sustainable the NGO is. (Beta= 0.313). One unit increase in finance will lead to a 0.313 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between the project's environmental impact and the sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more the NGO has projects that have an environmental impact, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.120). One unit increase in environmental impact will lead to a 0.120 increase in sustainability.

There is a positive relationship between stakeholder involvement and the sustainability of the NGO. This indicates that the more the stakeholders are involved, the more sustainable the NGO is likely to be. (Beta= 0.035). One unit increase in stakeholder involvement will lead to a 0.035 increase in sustainability.

In conclusion, all factors are involved in building sustainably in an NGO, but the most significant factors that impact sustainability are the stakeholder's involvement and the availability of funds inside the NGO.

Summary of the Quantitative Results

The results showed that this model is a good model and the variables truly represent sustainability as a whole. The linear regression showed that all factors are involved when it comes to building sustainability in the NGO. This proves that the hypothesis is valid.

The results highlighted the importance of financing for sustaining NGO projects, which can be explained by the fact that the situation in Lebanon has put limits on spending and NGO budgets, which has put limitations on funding projects, which in turn limited their sustainability. Given the rising need for NGO projects in Lebanon's challenging socio-economic situation, the need for funding begins.

The results of the linear regression showed that stakeholder involvement is another main factor that has an impact on the sustainability of NGOs. This indicates that the more the stakeholders are involved, the more sustainable the project is. This implies that the stakeholders must be more involved in the NGO and impose their roles quite often to make the NGO more sustainable.

Likewise, staff competence has a good impact on the sustainability of NGOs. This finding appears to be consistent with the other finding that most of the respondents agreed that staff knowledge of the most important issues for stakeholders is essential for the success of the project, which shows that competence is a combination of knowledge and qualifications, and both are equally important in project sustainability.

Finally, when asked to suggest ways through which the sustainability of Projects can be enhanced, the answers from the respondents showed that having strong relationships with the communities understanding their needs, and investing in their capacity building are important targets for sustainable NGO projects, besides prioritizing funding and the involvement of stakeholders. These recommendations are consistent with the previous results of the survey and solidify the need for these recommendations to ensure the prolonged sustainability of NGO projects in Lebanon.

Conclusion

The results of the quantitative research, specifically the regression, showed that there is a positive relationship between those factors and sustainability. This shows the importance of these factors in building sustainability in NGOs in Lebanon. Moreover, financing and stakeholder involvement are shown to be the most important factors when it comes to the sustainability of the NGOs.

The results showed that Financing is really important when it comes to building sustainability. Financing is a key factor for the sustainability of NGOs since an NGO requires different sorts of sustainability to keep going, especially during the economic crises that we are facing in Lebanon. This shows that NGOs in Lebanon should seek different sources of funding to keep going and be sustainable during these difficult times.

The second most important key factor is stakeholder involvement. Stakeholders need to get involved in many of the projects of the NGO to build sustainability and to keep going.

Staff competence is the third factor that contributes greatly to the project's sustainability. Staff competence and knowledge are considered important since they are a set of observable and measurable behaviors, and they mainly consist of knowledge, skills, and abilities that show what is required to be available in an individual to be able to perform his job role effectively to achieve key goals and improve performance of the NGO project team.

Recommendations

The findings of this research can provide recommendations for three practitioner parties. First, the NGOs and their project managers are recommended to benefit from the findings by applying the recommendations and the conclusions to prolong the sustainability of their projects.

Second, there is an implication that the stakeholders of projects, whether they were funders or partners, can better determine the criteria for a sustainable project. This would be especially important for them when they are surveying potential projects to fund and support.

The third implication is for the scholars and researchers in the field of project sustainability, who will learn more about the specific case of NGO projects in the Lebanese market and the factors that would enhance their sustainability. The researchers can use these new findings to build upon them and expand their research or make comparisons.

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